

ON THE MARGINS, THE SPEECH: THE LITERATURE OF PATRÍCIA MELO AS A REPRESENTATION OF THE INVISIBLE IN *LESS THAN ONE*

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ABSTRACT

The present work aims, from the reading of the novel *Menos que um* (2022), by Patrícia Melo, to promote some reflections about the importance of literature as an object of representation of reality and how issues of gender, class and race have been recurrent in the author's works. In addition to the novel's content being aligned with decolonial and intersectional thinking, the author's incursion into verisimilar work is also significant, as she appropriates a literature whose speech space denounces the permanence of colonial practices as a strong political project. Under the theoretical contribution of authors such as Teresa de Lauretis (1994), Françoise Vergès (2022), Mbembe (2021), I emphasize the idea that the maintenance of this social ill is also linked to necropolitics. Starting from events that feedback Brazilian illnesses perpetuated by colonial behavior to recent Brazilian issues, the characters involved in the novel, mainly Glenda and Jessica, intertwine, creating a kaleidoscope composed of the excluded, whose future seems to have no prospect of change for some.

Keywords: Intersectionality. Decolonialism. Female authority. Feminist literary criticism.

The Animal

Yesterday I saw an animal In the filth of the patio Picking up food among the debris. When I found something, I didn't examine it or smell it: I swallowed it voraciously. The animal wasn't a dog, It wasn't a cat, It wasn't a mouse. The animal, my God , was a man.

Manuel Bandeira , Belo Belo.

The idea of the animal-man, so often explored in Brazilian literature, can be experienced again through the comparison between two objects from the fictional field. Although the poem *O Bicho*, by Manuel Bandeira may have been written in the 1940s and represents a critique of the social order by the poet in that period, it seems to be directly linked to the present, since the country remains immersed in poverty and hunger. In the poem, the imagery construction provokes revulsion by the characterization of a hostile, filthy, chaotic environment, in addition to causing astonishment with the breach of expectations of the readers in the tenth verse, since after the poet mentions the words *animal*, *dog*, *cat* and *mouse*, it is through a vocative that surprises us with the revelation that that man-animal, picking up food among the debris, was actually a human being.

In addition to the zoomorphization of Naturalism, whose aspect is more centered on the individual's biological instincts, the idea of the animal-man brought here animalizes the human being due to degrading circumstances and absences, ranging from beans to the ceiling. In this bias, bringing the image of a person in a situation of extreme vulnerability and with a tone of denunciation, the novel *Menos que um* (2022), thirteenth book by Patrícia Melo, exposes the Brazilian tragedy related to people in a situation of social vulnerability. This is an ignored Brazil, since it is estimated that today there are more than 206 thousand people in this condition.

With that, from plastic to plasticity, the cover and the map of hunger hurt, since the book's art itself (fig. 01) presents a lot of meanings inherent to the events of Brazilian reality, as well as already inserting readers into the indigences of the characters; imagetically, a young man-animal is represented, similar to the one in Bandeira's poem, also already punished for the sufferings to which he is subjected. He is broken, he lacks fingers, part of his face, body and the right side of his brain – responsible for musical and visual skills –, that is, he is more concerned with solving immediate physical issues: hunger, beans, limiting it to (in)existence.

Figure 01: Book cover

Just like in the poem *O Bicho*, by Manuel Bandeira, he seems to be looking among the remains of plastic for something that can satisfy that hunger, something that someone would no longer need, which is why he discarded it. This man (animalized by circumstances) is less than one, he is not whole, he has no identity, he has lost his dignity, his clothes. They are the fragments of a human being who exists, but seems invisible, because he is totally ignored by society. However, something even more remarkable is knowing that this cover was inspired by a photo (fig. 02) captured by photographer Danilo Verpa, who works for the newspaper *Folha de São Paulo*. In this record, taken during the pandemic period, we see not only the young Reginaldo Gonçalves da Silva, 41, but also another man, with his back turned, picking up food among the debris in the filth of a courtyard in the richest city in Brazil. Both are surrounded by dumpsters, garbage bags, dirt from discarded materials, all close to an overpass.

Figure 02: Reginaldo, 41 years old, separates food that would go to waste in São Paulo.

Source: Folhapress/photography by Danilo Verpa

This photographic record is confirmation of a desolate scenario of systemic violence that endorses the need for changes, since the great protagonist of this very cruel reality – including in the novel – is social inequality, which coincidentally (or not) increased during the period of Covid-19 isolation. In addition, in some moments of the novel, several characters reflect on the fact that people confuse them with garbage, as unclean, being discarded socially.

In the literary field, the pains of hunger and misery intertwine in a scenario of chaos, bringing a human mosaic, whose subjectivities of the characters oscillate between (in)existence and suffering. Outside the fictional scope, according to Agência Senado, in 2022, the Second National Survey on Food Insecurity in the Context of the Covid-19 Pandemic in Brazil pointed out that 33.1 million people are not guaranteed what to eat — which represents 14 millions of new Brazilians facing hunger. According to the study, more than half (58.7%) of the Brazilian population lives with food insecurity to some degree: mild, moderate or severe ³. In the meantime, *Menos que um* brings together a collection of tragedies, composed of recent events and retold as remnants of a country that has not been able to resolve the issues of slavery until today, since the overwhelming majority of people living on the streets are black and the Racialized bodies are also socio-historical, as they carry the remnants of slavery.

According to a survey carried out by the UFMG Brazilian Observatory of Public Policies with the Homeless Population in 2022, until May alone, 5,039 thousand people went to live on the streets of the São Paulo capital. Thus, the homeless population in the city reached 42,240 people, a number greater than the almost 32 thousand, indicated by the last census of

³ <https://www12.senado.leg.br/noticias/infomaterias/2022/10/retorno-do-brasil-ao-mapa-da-fome-da-onu-preocupa-senadores-e-estudiosos>. Accessed on 03/03/2023.

the City Hall, released in January ⁴. Bringing the representation of such abject reality to the artistic field, considering that literature has the ability to boost reflection in order to sensitize and sensitize readers to the works, the analyzed narrative – literary and fictional – presents a plot whose complexity is faced with the difficulty of distinguishing fact from fiction. According to Eagleton:

The distinction between "fact" and "fiction", therefore, does not seem to us to be very useful, and one of the reasons for this is that the distinction itself is often questionable. It has been said, for example, that the opposition we have established between "historical" and "artistic" truth (...) In late sixteenth- and early seventeenth-century English, the word "novel" was used, which it seems, both for real and fictitious events, and even newspaper news could hardly be considered factual (EAGLETON, 2006, p. 2).

In this bias, such difficulty in distinguishing between fact and fiction pervades the actions and scenes narrated in the book *Menos que um*, because the stories intersect with the factual, revealing scenarios of chaos and deprivation. Because it is a delicate topic, it has rarely been approached so closely to reality, but a good novel is capable of transporting readers to incomprehensible experiences, even though they have never been through the situation, or been to those places. Patrícia Melo narrates a kaleidoscope of different daily struggles, inserting us in a reality as indigestible as it is ignored: a tragedy that jumps out at our eyes, because when we walk through the streets we see hunger, helplessness, the dehumanization of the people who inhabit this public space in a terrible shortage. The author talks about the physical and emotional deprivation of those rejected and the facets of the conditions that lead these individuals to become a street person, in addition to representing them with exact dimension, bringing their pain, their absence, their hunger and experiences with a fierce realism.

Everyone involved in the narrative seems to compose a social gear of marginalized, rejected people and, with this assertive look, Patrícia Melo constructs the subjectivity of each character without caricatures or romanticization, consequently tracing back an imaginary timeline from slavery to the present day. , because, as already mentioned, most people in this condition are black. According to the Brazilian Observatory of Public Policies with the Homeless Population, 68% of homeless people are black, 87% men, most aged between 18 and 59 years old and without complete primary education. In the novel, the abandoned, the despised, the encumbrances are brought: – cracudos, unemployed, drunks, foreigners, scavengers, girls, women, street vendors, orphans... people who, by force of circumstances, had to occupy the

⁴<https://observatorio3setor.org.br/noticias/numero-de-pessoas-em-situacao-de-rua-cresceu-no-brasil-em2022/#:~:text=Hoje%2C%20no%20pa%C3%ADs%20more%20de,in%20street%20of%20capital%20paulista> . Accessed on 03/02/2023.

streets in search of survival. With this, the protagonist is social inequality itself, since all individuals are important for the construction of the human mosaic, but they seem to be less than one, because they are erased, disappearing, losing their identities, their dignity:

Your mind frees itself from small bills, the eighty cents set aside for this, two twenty for that, you get rid of the economy of small things, what if I only eat the sausage, without the bread? How much is left for tomorrow? What if I cut out the coffee? And then, the most important thing: you stop being the guardian of little things, of two shorts, four underpants, five socks, a pair of black pants, soap, toothpaste, a comb, shaving equipment, photos of your wedding, photos of ice cream shop, photos that I didn't even look at anymore. (MELO, 2022, p.322)

In this passage, we managed to get a brief idea of how these people fade away, lose their dignity and identity as they leave behind their belongings and memories.

On the other hand, I highlight something that is quite marked in the novel: the lack of humanization of the militiamen; these torture, strangle, cut penises and kill without any sensitivity or empathy towards the next:

They killed people like João Henrique, Zélia's son, black and poor kids from the periphery, who they called bandidinhos. Marginal. Slag. and they charged for it. (...) Zeca, the owner of the bakery exactly at the moment when Marreco (a militiaman), with the police that Douglas already knew, raised a toast. And when asked the reason for the celebration, Marreco replied:
– Here we only celebrate two things: the boss's birthday and the death of a bandit. (MELO, 2022, p.160)

These figures are dehumanized, one of them is Marreco, who appeared driving a black zero Honda, a good that did not match his salary pattern:

“I'm a turner, I do cartwheels, I have my own business” (...) He attacked communism. Attack the Supreme. It attacked the vaccine. He attacked the quota system. Attacked the press. And he passionately defended the release of weapons: it is the effective policy to put an end to banditry, he believed. (...) “Start adding up. Put together the military police plus civil police plus members of the Armed Forces plus the entire family of each of these men. We are an army of nearly twenty million people. And we've already made a president. Do you understand what that means? (MELO, 2022, p.198)

Such characters seem to be at the service of the powerful and act by controlling places and bodies through discipline, atrocity and murder, in addition to reproducing models of genocide and massacres even with colonial characteristics, whose targets are mainly people from socially disadvantaged black skins. To support this survey, according to Achille Mbembe:

Policing and discipline techniques, in addition to the choice between obedience and simulation that characterized the colonial and post-colonial

potentate, are gradually being replaced by a more tragic alternative, given its extremism. Technologies of destruction have become more tactile, more anatomical and sensory, within a context in which the choice is made between life and death. If power still depends on strict control over bodies (or their concentration in fields), the new technologies of destruction are less concerned with inscribing bodies in disciplinary apparatuses than with inscribing them, at the opportune moment, in the order of maximum economy, now represented by the “massacre”. In turn, the generalization of insecurity deepened the social distinction between those who have weapons and those who do not (“weapons distribution law”). Increasingly, war is not taking place between armies of two sovereign states. It is fought by armed groups that act behind the mask of the State against armed groups that do not have a State, but that control quite different territories; both sides have as their main targets civilian populations that are unarmed or organized as militias. In cases where armed dissidents have not fully seized state power, they produce territorial partitions, achieving control over entire regions on the feudal model. (MBEMBE, 2018, pp.: 59 and 60)

Thus, these militiamen are a strong indication that they are at the service of someone who wants to exterminate minority social groups in order to clean the city from the presence of the excluded (according to the concept of necropolitics, defined by Achille Mbembe, the State decides who deserves to live and who deserves to die), that's why he makes victims daily. In this bias, the control of these more susceptible bodies – to biopower, sovereignty, the state of exception and the policy of death – occurs without punishment, since it is legitimized by the State itself.

Hypothetically, we relate places and facts narrated in the novel to the city and streets of São Paulo, as we can see the social hygiene actions carried out by Mayor Dória⁵, the presence of the priest (referring to the figure of Father Júlio Lancelotti who, precisely during the pandemic⁶, carried out and still carries out humanizing work). In addition to these factors, it brings the cartography of the largest *cracolândia* in Brazil – also located in São Paulo – and the occupations of uninhabited places, whose female leadership – mainly led by single mothers in reality – was metaphorized in the⁷ figure of the character Tula.

We also assume that the chronology of the facts narrated takes place in the pandemic scenario, since the character Douglas, the gravedigger, is appalled at the number of dead he had to bury:

The bodies are no longer placed on the funeral table, inside the chapel, to say goodbye to family and friends. They came packed in bags, inside sealed

⁵ <https://portal-justificando.jusbrasil.com.br/noticias/420362999/higienismo-de-doria-ea-populacao-de-rua> . Accessed on 9/2/2022.

⁶ <https://g1.globo.com/profissao-reporter/noticia/2021/04/21/padre-julio-lancelloti-mostra-trabalho-na-pandemia-dizem-que-sou-um-padre-maloqueiro.ghml> . Accessed on 9/2/2022

⁷ <https://oglobo.globo.com/brasil/noticia/2022/07/aqui-eu-renasci-nas-ocupacoes-de-sao-paulo-mulheres-e-maes-solo-sao-maioria.ghml> . Accessed on 9/2/2022.

coffins, which were not transported in coffins, but by tractors, in groups of eight, to be buried in mass graves. The queues for burials did not allow the gravediggers to drink even a glass of water in peace during the workday. (MELO, 2022, p.93)

In addition, I watched the news and noticed the exponential increase in people who lost their lives:

It was at night, at home, in front of the TV, that he watched the count of the dead on the news, that he understood the reality around him. The progress was astounding. From five thousand dead to twenty thousand. From twenty thousand to eighty thousand. From eighty thousand to one hundred thousand! Hundred thousand! Two hundred thousand! And it kept growing. Everywhere. Impressive data. Deaths of the day, moving average. Number of people infected. Propagation rates. Evolution charts. The numbers made headlines daily. All of this was destroying his faith, leaving him with a feeling of impotence and dread, which suffocated him on sleepless nights. (idem)

In the pandemic and isolation period, hundreds of people also lost their jobs, their homes, their families; in April 2023, there are already more than 700 thousand dead by Covid-19 in Brazil. With that, the whole set of actions caused appalling misery and, for those who no longer had an average social condition, the street was left: a public space through which everyone had to pass. Unfortunately, our eyes seem to ignore the scenario, either because of anguish, fear, or the impossibility of doing something to help.

In the fictional field, but in a hyper-realistic way, Patrícia Melo, who presents herself as a great writer of contemporary Brazilian literature – something that is confirmed, mainly in her last two published works: *Mulheres stackadas* (2019) and *Menos que um* (2022) –, presents equally cutting, laconic, corrosive narratives, but mainly in these two novels, violence, which is already a recurring theme in his writing, is presented in a systemic and constant way, as if the impetuosity of the processes that make up this violence and tortures reached death as a banal and inevitable spectacle. However, far beyond these already remarkable literary characteristics, the Brazilian author has brought important decolonial themes, providing greater engagement with issues of gender, class and race, assuming and confirming a prominent position and emerging as an important voice of female authorship.

Most of the actions take place on the street: a space, sometimes, personified, because at the same time that it excludes – all those who were expelled from home, expatriates, denied their existence –, it shelters people that society does not want; it is also a space that brings together the entire city, from the richest to the poorest. So there was everything on the street. Model, dondoca, crazy person, bandit, housewife. The gutter welcomes everyone like a generous mother (p.48). In addition, on the street, there were also those who transited, ignoring

the urban tragedy, since they were only concerned with arriving, leaving the office for lunch and returning to their homes at the end of the day.

It is interesting to point out that the author allows not only the representation of these characters, but also assigns them the narration in the first person, giving greater reliability to the actions. It is also significant to realize that the book is divided into three parts of seventeen chapters each, that is, the number corresponding to a particular presidential candidate in 2018 who, due to necropolitical actions and the extermination of minorities, aggravated the scenario of hunger and of misery in the country. Thus, the legitimization of violent behavior to defend private property in the face of this intensification of inequalities is apparent when we read:

“Where did you hide my gun?” He owned a hardware store. Shortly before, kids had entered the garage of his luxurious house, in the neighboring neighborhood, and stolen an old Browning (gun) from his car. (...) “it really seems that now there was a great tolerance by the State for types like that, who frequented shooting ranges and defended an eye for an eye, a tooth for a tooth”. (MELO, 2022, p.53)

This possible analogy is made so that it is clear who intensified such tragedies and how our vote may be able to at least minimize the suffering of the poorest. In addition, in some speeches reproduced by the militiamen, we perceive a similar association with the aforementioned political figure:

Most of the recordings showed semi-drunk men talking about canceled CPFs, denialist theories, rifle numbers, improvised graves, beatings, capsules collected before the forensics arrived, missed payments and military uprisings as if they were employees of a factory having a rough time and obscene at fraternization parties. (...) “They feel unattainable. Their crimes, when reported, are left to rot on special sticks. (ditto, p.293)

With this, we realized that the militiamen knew that they would get out of any situation with impunity, since the State legitimized this violent and corrupt behavior.

A human mosaic: non-persons?

It would be impossible to address all the characters in this work, but some stand out, such as Chilves: a black man, coming from the dump, lost a brother suffocated in the avalanche of garbage. He was Jessica's partner, with whom he had a son and, after being arrested, he woke up to political awareness: he died dreaming.

Seno Chacoy: Venezuelan, felt superior to homeless people. When he was employed, he would throw water on those individuals, wet the cardboard that served as their bed, calling

them ruffraff. He was clean, shaved and dressed with dignity. With the death of his wife, the stepson – a drug addict, who stole household items to bet on games of chance – returned to his mother's house and changed the locks so that his stepfather would not enter. After going to a shelter and complaining about the public services provided, he was unable to stay in the accommodation and ended up becoming a homeless person.

Post: professional pimp, abuser of Glenda. In the end, our desire for revenge comes true: he was beaten so badly that he seems to have actually died.

Rita: she was not homeless, had more space to speak, was a journalist and a friend of Glenda. Showed empathy towards Jessica when Chilves seemed interested in her. “– Think with me, Humble Teacher of Truth. I never had to sleep on the street. No one snatched a child from my arms. Be fucking nice to your girlfriend.” (p. 312). Rita's attitude indicates the possibility of us interpreting it as sisterhood towards Jessica.

Douglas: gravedigger, found it strange that a lady was living in the cemetery, but discovered that her son was buried there and had been killed by militiamen who wanted to “sanitize” the region. Adherent to the religion of good, he buried countless bodies, which represents the moment of the sanitary tragedy in Brazil. He also witnessed the collective mourning of people who, sometimes, could not even afford a coffin.

Representing people in situations of extreme vulnerability would already be very impactful from the point of view of violence experienced daily by these marginalized people. However, considering the analysis focus of the project I am part of under the guidance of Professor Maximiliano Torres: *What about feminisms, what are they intended for?*, I will raise, in a little more detail, questions pertaining to two characters in particular, they are Glenda and Jessica.

Less than One 's most intersectional and empathetic character

To begin studies on this character, who is the most intersectional in the novel, we turn to the definition by Patricia Hill Collins and Sirma Bilge when they state:

Intersectionality investigates how intersectional power relations influence social relations in societies marked by diversity, as well as everyday individual experiences. As an analytical tool, intersectionality considers that the categories of race, class, gender, sexuality, nationality, ability, ethnicity and age group – among others – are interrelated and mutually affect each other. Intersectionality is a way of understanding and explaining the complexity of the world, people and human experiences. (COLLINS and BILGE, 2021, pp.: 15-6)

With such information about intersectionality, we bring Glenda, who is representative of a strong transvestite, rejected by her family – something unfortunately commonplace for this part of the population. He met Jessica under the following circumstances:

Glenda distributed hygiene kits, along with Rita and the staff from the batbanho, a trailer with a water tank where two showers were installed and which drove around the city, hitched to an old pickup truck, offering free showers for people who lived on the street. One day, after Jessica had taken a bath and received new clothes, Glenda pulled her aside and said, look, daughter, you're like that, clean, you're very good. I organize some houses around the square and I need a helper. Now the two of them also cleaned a kitchenette that Glenda said belonged to “a classy businessman”, but who, in reality, was a sickly waiter. (...) “I've lived on the street, Glenda had told him, “I know very well what it's like to be let go, we get used to the bagaceira, the lice, the bodum, but to serve my fine clientele you have to smell good, clean poor style, did you?” (MELO, 2022, p.41)

In the literary representation of the novel, we perceive the need to deconstruct prejudice in relation to this community, since Patrícia Melo brings Glenda as the most human, most empathetic character in the entire plot. When she was still in a situation of lesser poverty, that is, when she at least had a place to live in the boarding house, she was the one who offered – within her financial possibilities – food and hygiene kits for women living on the streets. Unfortunately, in a sequence of routine actions in relation to this part of the LGBTQIAP+ community, Glenda ended up suffering a series of physical and emotional violence. However, before the age of twelve, when discovering herself a woman, readers are faced with this moving account of the character:

It was as if that dress were a female soul looking for a body and, as she felt it slipping over her head and molding itself to her torso, as if it had been made to measure, she almost heard the perfect fit click between that pink beauty and her true feminine identity. (MELO, 2022, p.139)

In this sense, it should be noted that the very identification of this person with the female gender could generate misogyny, lack of acceptance towards her, in addition to revealing open prejudice by a large part of society, as in this scene: “– Traveção! – shouted the mason hanging from a scaffolding at the work Central Park do Brasil” (p.237). In order to be reliable in relation to what the most recent studies on feminism theorize, it is essential for our reflections to highlight this character, since the discussion about gender is a key point for us to raise this hypothesis of violence towards Glenda. Reinforcing this survey in a theoretical way, we resort to what Teresa de Lauretis says:

(1) Gender is (a) representation – which does not mean that it does not have concrete or real implications, both social and subjective, in people's material lives. Quite the opposite. (2) The representation of genre is its construction – and in a more common sense it can be said that all Western art and high culture is a record of the history of this construction. (3) The construction of the genre is taking place today at the same pace as in the past, such as the Victorian era, for example. And it continues to occur not only where it is expected to happen – in the media, in public and private schools, in the courts, in the nuclear, extended or single-parent family – in short, what Louis Althusser called "the ideological apparatuses of the State". The construction of gender is also carried out, although in a less obvious way, in the academy, in the intellectual community, in avant-garde artistic practices, in radical theories, and even, in a very marked way, in feminism. (4) Paradoxically, therefore, the construction of gender is also done through its deconstruction, that is, in any discourse, feminist or not, that sees gender as just a false ideological representation. Gender, like the real, is not only the effect of representation, but also its excess, that which remains outside discourse as a potential trauma that, if/when not contained, can disrupt or destabilize any representation. (LAURETIS, 1994, p.209)

By bringing the theory of this construction, or even the recognition of gender defined by Lauretis to the fictional field of the novel *Menos que um*, the definition would represent the need for identification in the life of the character Glenda, who abandons the nickname that the family chose, assumes her social name and begins to live with his true identity. But some questions remain unanswered: Why do the aggressors in this community act with such cruelty? Why so much hatred towards the feminine elements present in these bodies? Could it be the fact that they also carry characteristics of women and, therefore, such aversion? Although attempts are made to raise these questions, there is no justification for so much violence. From this perspective, Françoise Vergès, in the work *A Feminist Theory of Violence*, emphasizes the need to consider broad factors to cover protection for all women, which is why she points out:

Trans people and those who refuse to identify with a gender are the most targeted by violence, but, as not all attacks on women – cis, trans, lesbians – and non-binary people, within a year, are reported, and considering that non-white women are underrepresented in these numbers – as the violence committed against them, including murders, do not receive the same attention – it would be necessary to include race, class, gender and sexuality discrimination in these estimates to address systemic violence against women. (VERGÈS, 2021, p.83)

From this perspective, Vergès endorses what was problematized by the author, representing the murder of a trans woman as something trivialized and, worse, due to the fact that Glenda was killed by militiamen, we realize that they still placed themselves in a position of moral saviors and good morals, exterminating a person with that sexual orientation. Thus,

according to Vergès, we infer that plural feminisms need to encompass and account for all types of violent actions against women as gender factors, aggravated by class and race.

Following real-life statistics, Glenda had already prostituted herself and Poste, her former pimp, constantly exploited her. One night, he entered the simple pension where she lived, violently assaulted her and took her wallet. For this, she received eighty-seven stitches on her face and was told that she would change her name to Lady Frankenstein. When she was in the hospital, she was humiliated by doctors and other employees, since she was admitted to the male ward and, although she had informed her social name, she was only called Weverton Freitas: “She said, indignant, that they did not accept her social name (. ..) They didn't allow her to go to the female ward (Cf. MELO, p.70). After the episode, many began to call her a “monster”. This scene makes us reflect on the violence committed against these bodies. Glenda was in a hospital environment in which she should have been well cared for, respected, welcomed, however, she was humiliated, her social name was not respected, she was rejected.

After a mess on the street, Glenda was approached by militiaman Cleber, who said: “– You are under arrest!” (Melo, p.280). In this speech, Cleber refers to her as a man, demarcating the prejudice and exclusion of people with this sexual orientation. Such lack of respect for this group of the LGBTQIAP+ community reveals an even more violent condition in relation to black and poor people, that is, racial, class and identification with the female gender factors intensify the trivialization of practices of violence .

Due to these factors, we also infer that there is an extreme trivialization of the murders of people belonging to the aforementioned community. Such trivialization occurs mainly in relation to transvestites, whose bodies – which preserve the identification with the feminine – are even more vulnerable; most of these people die young, without the right to a decent burial. Scars and sequins were nearly all that was left of Glenda. (idem, p.314), who died tragically; she was murdered by the militiamen, but the most shocking thing is knowing that she was castrated and, even after being killed, she was humiliated by the assassins.

“He's a transvestite,” added Marreco. And there's a reporter (Rita) who's making a hell of a fuss about this shit. You know, these perverts these days are worth more than me, than you, than anybody. “And if it was black, it was worth twice as much,” added Cleber. (ditto, p.295)

Still in this scenario of cruelty towards the trans community, in an interview with CNN⁸, lawyer Marina Ganzarolli, president of the OAB-SP Sexual and Gender Diversity Commission, stated that:

The life expectancy of this group is comparable to figures from the Middle Ages. “The T population in Brazil has a life expectancy of less than 35 years, which is comparable to the life expectancy of the Middle Ages, when there was no penicillin or basic sanitation.” Still according to the specialist, data from the National Association of Transvestites and Transsexuals (ANTRA) that 90% of the T population is in a situation of prostitution. According to her, the number reports the lack of opportunities in the job market for this group. The scenario, however, is in the process of changing. (CNN Brazil)

This reality is as cruel as it is ignored, since the violence of unemployment, exclusion, lack of opportunities, prejudice and abomination towards the T population reflects a behavior that goes beyond misogyny; it is gratuitous hatred, persecution, transphobia and, above all, the lack of empathy for human beings. In this sense, readers are faced with indignation in the face of these murders and, with the rawness and representation of Patrícia Melo's writing, they feel in tune with the characters of the novel.

Glenda was missing for some time, but when her body was found, there was a simple burial so that readers could say goodbye symbolically to the character:

At that moment, Jessica took a plastic bag full of sequins from her pocket that she had found in one of the drawers in the closets of Glenda's apartment and spread them over the grave. The place was filled with colored dots that, in contrast to the dark earth, sparkled in the sun. (MELO, 2022, p.317)

It is a poetic scene whose description is emotional, however, in addition to literary experimentation, it is possible to reflect on issues that are not commonly discussed because of prejudice, hypocrisy and false moralism. Unfortunately, in 2023 there is still a lot of neglect and exclusion of this group, but one of the roles of literature is to bring any subject, hitherto virtually ignored, as a form of reflection and analysis.

Jessica: a teenager in (re)construction

This character is a fifteen-year-old girl who ran away from home after being abused numerous times by her uncle (her aunt's husband) and, in a sequence of tragedies, ended up becoming a homeless person. When Jessica went to visit Glenda, hospitalized because of Poste's

⁸ <https://www.cnnbrasil.com.br/nacional/expectativa-de-vida-de-trans-no-brasil-se-equipara-com-idade-media-diz-advogada/>. Accessed on 03/04/2023.

aggression, we found out why she had lost the ability to express herself, as the revelation to readers began when a teacher argued with her:

“Are you having a problem at home?” But she didn't know how to respond. He hated every word in that story: chu-pa... the... dick... of... your... fake little uncle. Lick lick. He was going to tell Glenda that she too had a Pole in her life. The truth is that, on the street, there is not a single woman who does not have the same or worse story. A Husband Of My Mother. A stranger you have to call Uncle just because he crawled into Aunt Broken Glass's Heart's bed. And who suddenly wants to put the dick in his mouth. Even today she had nightmares about that boyfriend of her aunt's, that man who smelled like Milk of Roses and who was loved in the neighborhood, a respected taxi driver. (MELO, 2022, p.73)

Jessica's situation does not happen in an isolated or rare way, since most aggressions against girls and women occur inside the victims' homes and, in most cases, by a parental member of the victim, or by someone known to the family. . Following this statistic, in the work *A feminist theory of violence* , Françoise Vergès highlights:

Every day, on average, 137 women are murdered in the world by someone close to them. Among these, more than a third are murdered by their spouse or ex-spouse. Around 15 million adolescents (aged fifteen to nineteen) worldwide have been subjected to forced sexual intercourse (penetration or forcibly imposed sexual acts) at some point in their lives. (VERGÈS, 2021, p.83)

He got involved with Chilves, another homeless person, but when he was arrested, Jessica became vulnerable, which is why she ended up triggering her addiction to crack and started to prostitute herself to support her addiction – even though she was pregnant with a baby. Even though she was aware that she was offering her own body in exchange for little money, here we are faced with the subjectivity of the teenager's behavior, who kept her thoughts confidential:

Guys could fuck your body. For a market price, they could squeeze, kiss, suck, lick and mount. Everything included in the package. But, inside her mind, there was a little sign hung by herself: No strangers allowed. Her thoughts, her ideas, her projects, everything there was like a room she kept all to herself. Braided. (MELO, 2022, p.151)

She was enticed by the character Poste, the same as Glenda's aggressor, who ended up managing, as a pimp, her earnings from working as a prostitute. So, with the false idea that he was protecting her from street violence, all Poste had to do was drink or snort and the conversation was already different: my wife this-and-that, he said: “Next time, I'll cut your throat, threaten .” (Melo, p.152). Being a woman is already a perilous factor in relation to the

objectification of bodies, vulnerability to aggression, harassment and rape. Thinking about all these systemic violence is already very distressing, however, if we add such issues to the susceptibility of women living on the street, everything becomes even more tragic. In the novel, some women found themselves in a degrading situation, because when they were not under the command of an exploitative pimp, violence continued to come from all sides, so they tried to protect themselves in every way:

Many women on the street had no owners. They carried stilettos. They slept on the blade. Some went crazy. Or they dressed like grown men. There were also those who avoided any type of hygiene to cause disgust. They reeked of shit. Still, many were attacked at night when they slept. (ditto, p.153)

Here we perceive the degradation of these vulnerable female bodies that need proper hygiene, especially during the menstrual period, but which, in addition to not having such dignity, were kept fetid to avoid rape. This reflection by Jessica gives us a brief idea of how painful the lives of these people must be, especially that of women. In addition, thinking about the cartography of cities, some spaces are even more dangerous, because they are less crowded and lit, or because they are hostile towards the marginalized. Thus, according to Vergès:

City architecture was not designed to encourage a relaxed social life; she is hostile to women, particularly women of color, homeless, refugees, elderly, immigrants, poor, disabled, black and Arab people. The city is organized to obstruct the circulation of these people, it has “invisible walls” that racialized women and children must learn to identify in order to get around and avoid. (VERGÈS, 2021, p.82)

With this metaphor of “invisible walls” by Vergès, we realize that the streets offer even more hostility and risks to girls like Jessica, whose life was a succession of sufferings. In which places could she and so many other marginalized people in the same situation remain without disturbing others?

Even when she was pregnant, Jessica was taken to an evangelical recovery clinic for addicts, whose nickname was Casa do Esplendor Divino. This mean and corrupt clinic received funding from the State, but kept the inmates in private prison so that they would work in a forced way: “The monitors call it therapy, but the name is different: slave labor” (Melo, p.207). The inmates had to wash stones, paint walls with whitewash and were subjected to penance every time they broke some internal regulation, which almost always changed:

For eating out of hours. For having had an epileptic seizure. For having “stolen” a bag of biscuits in the kitchen. For being caught naked, admiring her seven-month pregnant belly in front of the mirror. For having gone into the woods at Bible reading time. For refusing to take the medicine. For trying to

kill himself with tranquilizers. For listening to funk. For not singing hymns in church services. For having answered the monitor. Or stopped responding. For trying to run away. The scope of punishments wasn't much different from a game without rules. What was allowed yesterday is now forbidden. (MELO, 2022, p.204)

The girls were assaulted, physically and emotionally tortured, as they were kept away from family life and from the possibility of denouncing irregularities:

“Demon whore, do you think you can fight against the power of God?”, asked the monitor after finding, under Jessica's T-shirt, a sheet of paper which read: “They beat the inmates. Get me out of here.” Jessica, on that occasion, was in the room where she would receive the weekly video call from Glenda and Chilves, which ended up being suspended as a punishment. For the next few days, completely isolated in the contrition house, defecating and urinating into a hundred-gallon oil can, she thought she would go crazy. Who would die of despair. (ditto, p.208)

Many interns were assigned to manufacture sausages with the aim of being sold, further increasing the clinic's earnings. When Jessica managed to escape, she tried to communicate and report the irregularities to a journalist, who reported her, which is why she was forced to return to prison. Only after complaints from Rita, another journalist and friend of Glenda, did Jessica manage to be freed. Upon arriving at Casa do Esplendor Divino, Rita asked “What are those purple spots on your shins?” and Jessica replied: “Broomed. Here everyone gets caught. For any reason.” (Melo, p.240).

Upon being released from prison, she found Chilves – fresh out of the penitentiary system; It is interesting to reflect that at least when I was in prison, in jail, I had a roof over my head and food, so was it such a great privilege to win freedom? What does it mean to be free in this environment of extreme hardship? So, even though Jessica was already at an advanced stage of pregnancy, she went to sleep with Chilves in the street on the cardboard.

A short time later, the girl went into labor and went to the hospital, where she experienced obstetric violence, when the tears returned to her face and she began to express herself again. However, after a few days of hospitalization, she received the news that she could not keep custody of her own daughter because she was addicted to crack and because she did not have the financial and emotional conditions to offer the child a dignified life:

The judge advised that Lorraine would be sent to a shelter. And that Jessica should undergo drug recovery treatment before getting custody of her daughter. Jessica couldn't believe her ears. Until days ago, Lorraine was inside her belly. It was as if they were saying to him: let's take your lung to the shelter. We're going to get you out of your brain for a while. (...) he only handed over Lorraine after the judge threatened to suspend her right to visit the girl at the shelter. In the elevator, held in Chilves' arms, Jessica was

sobbing. He vomited on the sidewalk. Then he sat in front of the courthouse door, refusing to leave. (MELO, 2022, p.289)

After that first cry, the tears came, it is not known if for Lorraine (the baby), for Glenda (her missing friend), or if for herself (Melo, p.315); in fact, she wept because of life, because of the miserable circumstances, because of the violence she had suffered, because of the whole tragedy that her existence had become. At the end of her trajectory, she got custody of her daughter after being reunited with her mother and, thus, was able to offer a home, food and care for the baby. In addition, she moved in with her mother, Zélia, at Douglas's house, returned to her studies and was very dedicated to her lessons. Douglas once thought:

I wish Danny (Douglas' daughter) was like Jessica, so devoted to school. When Danny was born, he promised himself: this one will study, this one will go to university. His dream was for Danny to break the mold of his lineage. First to graduate. But, judging from the pace of the carriage, it was Zélia who would experience this joy first. (MELO, 2022, p.360)

Therefore, when we think about the VII SEPPLIN proposal – *projects for a new time and solutions for the future*, education is the only mechanism capable of symbolizing the possibility of change in people's lives. Symbolically, education and class consciousness are addressed in the novel in order to lead to the most victorious outcomes of the characters who had the opportunity to follow such paths.

Final considerations

There are countless themes that can be analyzed in *Menos que um* (2022). In this excerpt, I tried to show how the author makes use of fiction that emphasizes the invisibility of people in situations of vulnerability and violence to which they are subjected on a daily basis. This, through the rawness of Patrícia Melo's writing as a way of decolonizing the thinking of those who maintain this structure of class, race and even gender, since everyone has a voice. From the perspective of Glenda and Jessica's eyes and actions, so many people were represented – for suffering countless negative consequences of a toxic patriarchal structure towards people like them. These two characters provide us with rich material for analysis, so there is still much to be explored in relation to them.

It is interesting how the author manages to deconstruct the narratives that may have already addressed similar issues, bringing the speech of each of these characters as a strong element of social denunciation. In this way, the writer also deconstructs the narratives with a single point of view, demonstrating not only the malleability to create fictions, but also

implementing an engaged literature, since it maintains direct dialogues with decolonial factors, race, gender and class. The novel is sensitive from the point of view of the transformation that education is capable of promoting, since, in addition to the character Jessica, the Iraquitana writer also represents this possibility of change, since at the end of the author's text, he publishes a homonymous book, bringing metalanguage as a way of representing the invisible under the gaze of an invisible.

The narrative spaces represent the cartography of violence and Patrícia Melo brings this structure ingrained in Brazilian culture, therefore, the novel even resembles a dystopia, however it tells part of the Brazilian reality, since they are similar to announcements of imminent tragedies. Unlike the canonical themes, in relation to interpersonal relationships, this author's literature by itself already represents the adversities in different social strata and, therefore, there is still much to be explored in terms of writing and theoretical analysis, especially in this work.

Therefore, with a laconic writing – with her cutting literature, corrosive humor and the presence of constant violence, sometimes bringing death as a spectacle for those who read the works – the writer confirms her consolidation as a great author of Brazilian literature contemporary, representing characters of different classes, races, ethnicities, or sexual orientations. Thus, Patrícia Melo occupies a prominent place in Brazil, being translated to numerous countries as well. Thinking about these issues makes us understand the importance of this great author's writing, as it makes the country's marginalized and invisible peoples visible to the world, the animal-men, showing not only what is most beautiful, attractive and touristic, but revealing the true face behind what is sometimes deliberately hidden, ignored, that is, the speeches from the margins, by the margins.

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